

Patients' work and fluid trajectories: Access to medicines for oncological and rare diseases in Russia

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ABSTRACT

Health policy studies usually conceptualise access to medicines as a result of the institutional configuration of policies, legislation, and pharmaceutical markets. This study adopts a different approach that stems from the sociology of health and Science and Technology Studies (STS). Based on an ethnographically inspired qualitative research of access practices of patients with oncological and rare diseases in Russia, we argue that access to medicines is a fluid and unstable trajectory constructed by the everyday practices of patients. Instead of seeing patients as passive recipients of institutionally arranged access, we focus on their practices of building access and identify four types of work they do to steer their access trajectories in the desired direction. These types of work include persisting work, complying work, adjusting work, and knowing work. In many studies of access, these types of work remain invisible, and thus the efforts and skills that patients need to make access possible remain unnoticed, undervalued, and unaccounted for.

1. Introduction

Access to medicines is a major priority on the global health agenda, be it access to the antiretroviral therapy, the latest generation of anti-malaria medicines, or COVID-19 vaccines. In the field of health policy studies one of the most influential approaches to analyse problems of access to healthcare more broadly are 5-As suggested by [Penchansky and Thomas \(1981\)](#). The 5-As of national healthcare systems include availability, accessibility, accommodation, affordability, and acceptability. Studies conducted using this approach view access to medicines from the “front stage” – through the work of institutional actors like policies, policymakers, pharmaceutical companies, and legal agreements. We, in contrast, follow public administration literature that emphasises the importance of patients in (co)producing public services. In line with that we look at access to medicines from the “backstage” by studying the mundane practices of patients, doctors, and activists. To that purpose, we draw from Science and Technology Studies (STS), and we structure our theoretical lens through the concept of trajectories, first suggested by [Strauss et al. \(1982\)](#). They defined trajectories as results of organisation of work continuously performed by various participants of the medical process, including doctors, technicians, patients, and their

relatives. Relying on this theoretical background, we aimed to understand how, in practice, patients with rare and oncological diagnosis construct and maintain access to medicines. To do that, we analysed patients' access trajectories and identified types of work done by patients and their families and how these types of work intertwine and enable access.

Although our theoretical framework implies that many actors shape patients' trajectories of access to medicines, in this study, we focus on accessing work done by patients, their families, and patient communities. Specifically, we studied access trajectories to medicines for the treatment of oncological and rare diseases in patients in St. Petersburg, Russia. The Russian medical context is an illustrative setting for studying access to medicines. Existing research demonstrates substantial social, political, and economic shifts in the biosocial lives of Russian citizens in recent decades (see [Zvonareva, 2020](#) for the study of pharmaceutical politics; [Endaltseva, 2020](#) for the study of a patient organisation's identity and care; [Temkina and Rivkin-Fish, 2020](#) for research of consumer practices in maternity care). These shifts present an excellent opportunity to observe trajectories of access to medicines in the making. In addition, we aim to not exoticise the Russian context but to use it as an example for our theoretical contribution to the understanding of access

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to medicines.

We begin by outlining the system of Russian drug provision. Then we present the theories we draw from: the health policy studies perspectives on access, literature on co-production and Science and Technology studies (STS), and the trajectories framework. After describing the methodology, we present the results of our analysis. We delineate four types of access work done by patients and their families and to show the interconnectedness of these different types of work, we present a detailed analysis of one trajectory of a patient with phenylketonuria (PKU). We finish this paper by discussing the theoretical insights that our constructivist study of access to medicines provides.

2. Infrastructure of access to medicines in Russia

In Russia, access to medicines is arranged differently for in-patients and out-patients. While drugs needed for the former are (almost) totally covered by the Compulsory Medical Insurance (CMI), drugs for the latter are to be purchased out of pocket by patients unless they belong to one of the groups entitled to receive prescribed medicines for free, such as veterans, people officially recognised as disabled, children up to 3 years old, etc. Since our paper focuses on patients with rare and oncological diseases, further we outline infrastructural features relevant to them.

Pharmaceutical treatment of patients with rare diseases is considered outpatient care and thus can only be covered by the state for patients entitled to such coverage. Whether a patient is entitled to free medicines depends on their diagnosis, disability status, age, and some other social characteristics. Importantly, medicines for different groups of patients are financed from different sources, from dedicated federal funds to regional budgets and managed by different state agents, from state owned charities to regional healthcare authorities. This diversity greatly influences availability and timeliness of drug provision. For instance, children under 18 diagnosed with spinal muscular atrophy are provided medicines by federal funds relatively quickly and consistently, while adults with the same diagnosis are often confronted with delays and refusals from regional authorities responsible for drug provision. Consequently, there are always patients who do not fall into “right” categories and have to struggle to get access to otherwise hardly affordable medicines.

Unlike treatment of rare diseases, treatment of cancer is included in inpatient care and thus cancer medicines are covered by CMI. CMI was introduced in 1993 and, according to the Federal Law N326-FZ¹, it finances healthcare provision to all Russian citizens and foreigners permanently or temporarily residing in the country. Operation of CMI is sustained by employer insurance contributions and state budgetary funding meaning that patients incur no out-of-pocket payments. The same federal law stipulates that CMI must cover an extensive list of services, specified in medical standards developed by the Ministry of Healthcare including provision of medicines for inpatient treatment (i.a. cancer medicines). However, scholars report that the size of funding available does not correspond to healthcare needs in practice, which results in healthcare services being unavailable or severely delayed (Shishkin, 2018). Furthermore, there is geographical inequality in services and pharmaceuticals available for inpatient treatment.

Thus, both patients with rare and patients with oncological diseases are bound to experience inconsistencies between their needs and healthcare services and pharmaceuticals provided to them.

¹ [Federalnyi zakon ot 29.11.2010 N326-FZ ‘Ob obiazatelnom meditsinskom strakhovanii v Rossiiskoi Federatsii’ \(2011\)](#) [The federal law of the Russian Federation of 29.11.2010 N326-FZ ‘About Compulsory Medical Insurance in Russian Federation’]

3. Theoretical background

Levesque et al. (2013) introduced one of the most influential health policy frameworks for conceptualising access to healthcare; they defined access “as the opportunity to reach and obtain appropriate healthcare services in situations of perceived need for care” (Levesque et al., 2013, p. 4). Based on previous health policy studies, including the work of Penchansky and Thomas (1981), the authors addressed access as an economic phenomenon, concluding that it has both supply and demand determinants. According to the Levesque et al. framework, access is realised when the system users’ abilities (demand) meet five dimensions of accessibility of healthcare services (supply). These five dimensions include:

1. Approachability – the existence of particular healthcare services is known to potential patients .
2. Acceptability – the services and mode of their provision are culturally and socially acceptable;
3. Availability and accommodation – the services are physically reachable within reasonable time;
4. Affordability – the cost of the services is economically acceptable;
5. Appropriateness – the quality, scope, correctness, and timeliness of the provided services are consistent with the needs of patients;

In health policy studies, access to pharmaceuticals has been conceptualised along similar lines. For example, Frost and Reich (2009) include the following components in their framework of access to health technologies (including medicines): availability, affordability, adoption, and architecture, where adoption includes activities that make the technologies accepted, and architecture includes the organisation of structures that manage access-related activities.

Although the discussed models pay attention to the wide variety of factors that constitute access to medicines on the macro level, in their analysis of these models Bigdeli et al. (2013) note that none of them “picture the full range of social and cultural constraints affecting access” (Bigdeli et al., 2013, p.696). They propose a paradigmatic shift from seeing patients as “passive users” towards recognising them as “expert patients” (Bigdeli et al., 2013, p.697). However, their access framework still places patients on the demand side of the access equilibrium and implies that access is rather created by institutional actors and not by the everyday routines of patients, doctors, and communities.

In contrast to that goes the notion of co-production, widely used in public administration literature. In this strand of research, the boundaries between healthcare providers and “consumers” are blurred and patients are viewed as participants of healthcare provision on all levels, from designing to assessing the services (Batalden et al., 2016). However, as Baim-Lance et al. (2019) point out, the meaning of co-production narrowed with time and came to signify patient participation in healthcare provision as “an add-on to improve services” (Baim-Lance et al., 2019, p. 129). In their research of an HIV-clinic, authors open up the concept once again and argue that patients inevitably create the healthcare service in their everyday, routine interactions with the point of care.

STS scholars make a similar argument. In studies of medical technologies, patients, along with doctors, nurses, and other healthcare providers are studied as enablers of the functionality of these technologies in their everyday practices. Oudshoorn (2008) showed how ambulatory ECG recorders only achieved their full potential if the involved actors, especially patients, do “much more work [...] than is represented in user guidelines and included in training sessions” (p.284). Engel et al. (2017) showed that, in a similar way, HIV testing was made successful via various strategies of mutual adaptation of the technology, local environments and patients’ needs. These STS studies focus on one material object and show that patients’ practices shape and enable this object’s functionality. We will take this argument a step further by studying how patients’ practices construct the access to medicines in a

complex landscape where numerous material and non-material entities must be aligned.

To structure our argument, we draw from the sociology of health, specifically from the concept of *trajectories* developed by Strauss et al. (1982) to study the management of (chronic) illness in hospitals. Based on observations of hospital settings and interviews with hospital personnel, the authors concluded that patients' illness trajectories depend not only on the development of the illness itself, but also on what *work* is being done by various actors to manage it. Notably, these scholars not only considered the work of medical staff, but also work done by patients themselves and their families. For example, within the hospital, Strauss et al. (1982) recognise machine work, safety work, comfort work, sentimental work, and articulation work, all done in diverse order that is negotiated between actors, influencing each other and health outcomes. While the term – trajectories – implies moving from beginning to end, this movement can be far from straightforward. Strauss et al. (1982) argue that this non-straightforwardness stems not only from the clinical complexity of a patient's case but also from the fact that not one person guides a patient from diagnosis to a successful discharge from the hospital; there are multiple people performing their (usually routinised) tasks. In other words, trajectories are *shaped* and not managed.

The concept of trajectories has been implemented not only in the study of hospital settings. First, it was applied to study the management of chronic illnesses at home (Corbin and Strauss, 1985, 1988). There, the research focus shifted from healthcare workers doing their work “*on, over, or through*” (Strauss et al., 1982, p. 9) patients to families that take over the task of supporting patients' lives and wellbeing at home. In this setting, different types of work were identified including illness-related work (e.g., taking medication, measuring blood pressure, etc.), everyday life work (e.g., running errands, bringing children to school, etc.), and biographical work (making sense of and reconstructing one's life). These types of work do not exist separately, but affect each other and respond to arising contingencies.

To address the limitations of the illness trajectories concept, Allen et al. (2004) developed the concept of care trajectories. They argued that the illness trajectory concept of Strauss and his team entails that “*the organisational context, interprofessional relationships and negotiation processes remain hidden from view*” (Allen et al., 2004, p.1012). To address that, Allen et al. suggested analytically positioning trajectories within the existing health and social care systems and paying close attention to their interconnections and dynamics. In line with Allen et al., Singh (2016) researched care trajectories for children with autism. She showed that parenting work to attend to these children's needs is imbued with love, hope, and dreams for children's futures, which significantly shapes their care trajectories. Parents strive to not just provide medical and social care, but also create access to education and promote a positive image of people with autism.

As we will see, access to medicines also entails striving to receive the best care possible, often beyond medicines per se. In this context, access to medicines includes not only drugs but also special nutrition, rehabilitation products, infusion procedures – products and services that are not medicines but that allow medicines to provide high-quality care. In our research, we draw on this delineated contextualised understanding of access to medicines and consider these special products and services integral to our discussion.

4. Methodology

To provide insights into patients' practices of constructing access to medicines, we conducted an ethnographically inspired qualitative study of patients affected by rare or oncological diseases in Russia. The qualitative methodology provided flexibility and openness of the research design and the ethnographic approach enabled deep immersion into the context and daily lives of patients (Atkinson and Hammersley, 2007), both needed to grasp people's mundane activities and doings.

4.1. The case

We chose to study patients with rare or oncological diagnoses as medicines they need for treatment are usually expensive and innovative, and accessing them requires significant effort from the patient's side, not just in Russia but in other settings as well (e.g., personalised cancer medicines in the Netherlands (Moors et al., 2018)). Thus, this case brings to fore patients' practices of building access to medicines.

4.2. Setting

We conducted our ethnographic work in the St. Petersburg metropolis. St. Petersburg was chosen due to the prominence of patient and charitable organisations' activities there. Although this paper does not focus explicitly on such organisations, we decided to approach the field through them because evidence from the grey literature and online sources demonstrated their prominent role in building access to medicines. However, because many patient activities and communication were happening online, we also traced patients' work of building access in digital spaces.

4.3. Data generation

We generated data primarily through semi-structured interviews with patients, their caregivers (in the case of children), and patient activists and observations of events organised by patient organisations. Digital spaces (websites and social media) used by patients were important data sources as well. Our understanding of the context was enhanced through informal conversations with the research participants.

The first step of the fieldwork initiated in March 2021 by researcher OT included building an understanding of the field through resources accessible online. We identified key patient organisations and collected as much information about their activities and problems as possible. Further, being knowledgeable about this field proved to be essential in establishing the reputation of a competent outsider, which helped to be trusted and to receive clarifications on subjects that are obvious for a patient but are not to an outsider. The second step of fieldwork performed in May 2021 involved approaching the selected organisations and patients. When contact with the initially selected patient organisation was established, further participants were recruited through snowballing. The third step in our fieldwork lasted from May 2021 to July 2021 and consisted of conducting interviews and observations.

The generated data consisted of 14 semi-structured interviews, five observations of conferences organised by patient organisations, and one participatory observation of a kick-off meeting for a collaboration project. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the fieldwork was conducted in a hybrid format: five interviews were held online, as well as five observed events. All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim. To save the conference materials for further analysis, researcher OT took notes during the presentations, recorded voice notes immediately following the events and wrote memos.

4.4. Data analysis

The analysis was guided by the theoretical approaches and research goals introduced above. The interviews were thematically coded using the Atlas.Ti software. The coding process was reiterative and collective. As a result of discussions among the research team the coding scheme underwent three rounds of changes. The coding scheme's transparency and applicability was ensured via independent coding of one of the interviews by three researchers.

4.5. Ethical concerns

In our research, we faced two major ethical concerns. First, we

conducted research in Russia – an explicitly non-democratic setting where a critique of the state and cooperation with foreign institutions can have severe repercussions. To ensure the safety of the research participants, we collected the minimum personal data possible, ensured anonymisation and secure storage of all the research data, and collected only oral instead of written informed consent. Second, patients' trajectories of access to medicines is a delicate topic that requires extra sensitivity. We ensured that the participants were familiar with the goals and procedures of the research before starting the interviews. We confirmed that participants were comfortable with being recorded and aware that they could stop recording at any moment or withdraw entirely from the research at any time. Furthermore, to compensate for the power asymmetries of the academic research, we shared with the research participants a non-academic report in Russian about the research findings.

4.6. Ethical approval

This study was reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Faculty of Health, Medicine & Life Sciences, Maastricht university (FHML-REC). The approval number is FHML-REC/2021/067. Besides, the study was additionally reviewed and approved by the Ethical Committee of the St. Petersburg Scientific Public Sociologist Organization ("SPAS"). Protocol number 1 from 24.05.2021.

5. Results

In our research, we have approached issues of access to medicines from the "backstage", focusing on the practices of patients and their families. In our analysis, we distinguished these practices into four categories or types of patients' work done to construct access to medicines. This section presents these types of work and explains how and why they are performed. To demonstrate how people choose and combine seamlessly and skilfully different types of practices and how trajectories and practices mutually shape each other, we conclude this section by presenting a case of one patient.

5.1. Types of patients' accessing work

5.1.1. Persisting work

One of the most striking and prominent features of patients' practices is repetition – going to doctors, doing medical tests, renewing prescriptions, writing complaints, and countless other activities. We named these practices the "persisting work". This work aims to push the system forward, get "unstuck" from its hurdles, or even push against it. Precisely by perseverance, patients achieve the desired goals, often not thanks to but despite the healthcare system's functioning.

The story of many patients, especially those with rare diseases, begins with an offset of worrying symptoms that do not make sense for medical professionals: standard treatments do not work, and common diagnoses are ruled out. While establishing a correct diagnosis is not easy for a doctor, patients must also do extensive work to be timely and correctly diagnosed. They start to routinely engage in practices that propel the clinical "investigation", mobilising various available resources. Initially, they act haphazardly, repeating the loops of referrals from general practitioners (GPs) to specialists, to multiple tests, and back to specialists or GPs. This vicious circle requires persistence: an appointment with the GP must be made which is not easy and instead, one might need to sit in a line for hours because appointment slots were unavailable, then the polyclinic² must be visited, referral to a specialist must be asked or even demanded, the waiting time for tests can be months, and the test results can be lost. Repeating these rounds is an

² Polyclinics are points of primary care where GPs usually conduct their work.

excruciating task also because there is no guarantee that the next turn will yield any effect. And, still, patients and/or their families keep doing it:

... the child was always sick. And all the tests, all those ... immunologists, allergists, wherever we went, no matter what place we turned to, no matter what examinations we did – [all clear], he was healthy enough to go to space. But that was wrong. But the child was sick. You have to find out, to look for the reason because the child is suffering. R_SpB_8

However, with time, patients not just repeat the circles of referrals but change and adjust their behaviour to increase their chances of success. For instance, they develop a specific strategy of communicating with doctors who do not to take their concerns seriously, trivialise their symptoms or attribute them to something mundane (like infant age) or less severe. A story shared by a patient's mother demonstrates the effectiveness of persistence – annoying doctors with the same complaints and concerns, appearing on their doorsteps time after time, may lead to success.

We went to a paediatrician; the paediatrician looked at us, we went to all the neurologists in our city, she [the paediatrician] said: "your child is normal, don't act stupidly". And then, when we came to the paediatrician once again, she said, "I'm so tired of you, go to geneticists, I no longer know where to send you". We opened the door to the geneticist, and the geneticist said from the door way: "Oh, this is our client". R_SpB_3.

Persistence practices are enacted not only to determine a diagnosis. For, establishing a diagnosis and receiving medicines once does not mean that they will be available regularly and timely. Persistence becomes especially visible when patients try to ensure the drugs' availability. For example, one of the ways to ensure that one's needs are "not forgotten" in the next procurement round is to remind of them to the healthcare officials responsible for the medicines procurement over and over again. As one of the interviewees shared, whenever the drug becomes unavailable in the pharmacy, they "go, make the round of a couple of well-known offices, say well-known words, show up once again: 'yes, it's me again, so and so'" R_SpB_6.

Persisting work is also dispersed over time. For some diseases, medicines are administered intravenously on a regular basis, which can only be done in a hospital. However, before admission a patient must provide results of blood and urine tests and negative tests for some contagious diseases to meet sanitary standards. If a caregiver accompanies a child, they also need to confirm absence of contagious diseases. Repeating these tests time after time to get the necessary infusions, with the prospect of it being a lifelong routine, requires dedication, perseverance, and significant time resources from patients and their caregivers.

5.1.2. Complying work

As described earlier, patients with oncological or rare diseases are usually entitled to receive free medicines from the state either via CMI or because they belong to one of the groups entitled for free medicines. However, to exercise their rights, patients must go through multiple bureaucratic procedures, often dictated by bureaucratic logic rather than medical needs or patients' interests. Besides being numerous, these procedures often change, stall, or even fail. Knowing which procedure to follow, how to follow it, and what the exact steps are, is highly valued knowledge among patients. Successfully completing the bureaucratic journey and obtaining the drug proves to be more than just following instructions step-by-step; understanding and following complex and patient-unfriendly instructions requires significant efforts from patients. We call these efforts the "complying work" because it emphasises how hard it is to merely "comply" with mandatory procedures and how to succeed patients must engage in practices that help them to keep the "compliance" on track.

The first example illustrates the scope of compliance work done by patients. It demonstrates the bureaucratic procedures one must follow if a rare disease is suspected and expensive treatment is needed. If the treatment falls into the official category of “*expensive*”, the medicines must be “*recommended for use*” by a federal clinic that specialises in this rare disease. Next, a medical panel of the hospital where the patient receives regular care, must confirm the recommendation. After that, the patient gets an official prescription and is entered into a special register. Only then the drug is procured and provided to the patient.

To receive the federal recommendation, a patient must undergo a complete medical examination in the federal clinic, usually situated in Moscow or St. Petersburg. CMI covers the travel costs, but only those by train, making such travel not feasible for many patients whose condition and location make long journeys simply life threatening.³ Thus, patients must mobilise their financial resources or ask patient organisations or charities for help with purchasing plane tickets and organising a visit to those federal clinics. In addition, the complete medical examination conducted there lasts for at least 10 days, meaning that patients must take time off work as a sick leave, which can be difficult for people with precarious or unofficial employment.

After successfully receiving recommendations for drug prescription, patients must present the recommendations to their physician, who must assemble medical panel which confirms the recommendation and issues an official prescription. However, panel assembly can be stalled and patients must address the issue with hospital administration. Receiving the official prescription, however, does not imply provision of the medicine automatically, for the patient must make its existence known to the healthcare officials responsible for register updates and medicine procurement:

And if a patient, for example, did not show any activity, did not declare himself in a formal manner, then our regions, unfortunately, still try to not include him in any register [of patients with rare disease].[...] Therefore, we help to draw up this first appeal: "I request to be included in the register, please provide the drug". R_SpB_5.

Sometimes, this proves to be enough for a drug to be provided. However, sometimes patients are denied the medicine under the pretext of a lack of financing. Since this is illegal, there are procedures to appeal these decisions.

This is precisely a situation illustrated in the second example. This example describes the practices patients need to engage in when procedures fail to work timely or not at all. In that case, patients first need to restore the procedures with which they have been complying by adhering to official guidelines for appeal, complaining, and enforcing the law. Most frequently it is needed when the prescription is issued but the prescribed medicines are not available in pharmacies which is often due to bureaucratic disarray. Sometimes, tender procedures for medicine procurement are not initiated in time by regional healthcare officials; sometimes, there are no bidders because the prices suggested by the authorities are not competitive. Sometimes, patients suspect that healthcare bureaucrats stall the provision process deliberately to save money on the region's budget. To fight the consequences of this disarray, patients file official complaints and claims, write official letters to regulatory bodies, and even go to court:

We start an active correspondence with the region: patients write, patient organisation writes, we are constantly asking ... reminding that there are laws, that the law must be executed, that the patient must be helped; we always try to resolve [the problem] peacefully ... with the region. But when it cannot be done peacefully, then the patient certainly goes to court. R_SpB_1

The practices we identified as complying work are incredibly

exhausting and excruciating for patients. Procedures that are supposedly designed to provide them with the necessary medicines turn out to be a dark bureaucratic labyrinth in which patients easily get lost.

5.1.3. Adjusting work

Not every problem that patients encounter can be solved by following official procedures. Sometimes, these methods prove inefficient or there is simply no officially designated way to solve a problem. In these cases, patients engage in practices that allow them to adapt to the situation, adjust the system through informal means, and sometimes even adjust themselves to the circumstances in which the healthcare system has put them. We decided to call these practices “*adjusting work*”.

Overcoming obstacles in trajectories of access to medicines in a formal way, (e.g., by following the procedures or by appealing the rights violation) requires significant time and effort. Often, patients cannot afford to spend these resources without damaging their health. Thus, they resort to practices that allow them to temporarily resolve the problem and address the system's hurdles while the temporary remedies are in effect. These practices of adapting to the system are enacted collectively – by patient communities – and individually. On the collective level, for example, when some patients face delays with drug provision, their peers are ready to share their personal reserves:

I just give an impulse in our chat saying "the medicine is needed", and they start looking. Some people literally donate their own [medicines], this happens often, they just take [medicines] away from themselves. Some people often have a situation, you know, they have a prescribed drug but it doesn't suit this patient, for example. R_SpB_4.

This practice is enabled by and constructs trust and solidarity between patients: either a person expects that the borrowed number of medicines will be returned later or if there is no such expectation, people are simply moved by a shared experience of uncertainty and precarity.

On the individual level, some patients go as far as adjusting their drug dosage to “*survive*” until the moment when the medicines become available again:

– I already know that if I have received the drug – it's good, I should use it. Closer to January and June, I need to form a stash ... steal a little from myself, so that in, so to speak, lean months when it [medicine] is not there, I have something to infuse.

Q: So how does it happen, you infuse a smaller dose or you buy more?
– Well, I have to infuse a little less, I have a little smaller dose, yes. R_SpB_6.

Although it is a dangerous practice, it is deemed an inevitable or necessary evil, a reasonable alternative to, on the one hand, not having the drug at all, and, on the other hand, panicking and “*creating a fuss*”.

The obstacles and delays in the system can also be addressed by adjusting the system itself. This is, to a certain extent, possible via informal means. Examples include utilising personal connections, building a confidential relationship with doctors and healthcare authorities, and sometimes even resorting to informal payments.

While the previously described practices can be seen as adaptation to the ways the healthcare system functions or as finetuning and “*greasing*” this “*machine*” to the individual needs and circumstances of patients, some patients' practices can be regarded as compensation mechanisms for elements entirely lacking. Typically, these practices are not focusing on securing access to medicines per se, rather they concern services unavailable in the Russian healthcare system or services of insufficient quality. To receive these services patients rely on informal communities to find the necessary professional skills (e.g., oncologists answering questions in WhatsApp chats) or to serve as the service provider (e.g., of nutritionist support as in the following example:

³ For instance, the train from Vladivostok to Moscow takes 7 days.

There is one granny [...] in the Russian-speaking community, who got trained as a nutritionist and now she provides consultations [to us], she looks at nutrients, she understands the test, but, well, it's just one person, so we lack [nutritionist support]. R_SpB_3

Adjusting work is a constant work of creatively circumventing, adapting, and shaping access to medicines. These inventive and even innovative practices emerge due to mutual trust and a sense of cooperation. However, they cannot fully compensate for the problems in the Russian healthcare system. Instead, they serve as a safety net for hard times and ways to adapt to everyday uncertainty and hardship.

5.1.4. Knowing work

Above, we have discussed how patients persist in propelling further their diagnostic “*investigation*” or securing their access to the prescribed medicines. We also discussed how they follow the official procedures, re-establish their rights to be provided with medicines, adjust to the system’s rigidities, and bridge its gaps. However, all these actions require patients to engage in the “*knowing work*”. This group of practices encompasses everything patients do with helpful knowledge: collect, combine, produce, utilise, share, etc. This knowledge that helps patients to get access to medicine is a very particular assemblage: it includes medical knowledge about the disease, hands-on experience of practical aspects of living with the disease (e.g., what to eat, which rehabilitation tools to use, etc.), knowledge of legislation and bureaucracy-related issues, and knowledge about ways to compensate for imperfections of the latter.

Assembling this set of knowledge is not an easy task for patients. Doctors usually serve as the first contact point for newly diagnosed patients and their families. However, doctors cannot provide patients with all the information they need as their knowledge of bureaucratic hurdles and practical issues of dealing with the disease is limited. In addition, appointments are usually too short for doctors to explain medical information to patients in an accessible and consistent way. Thus, to compensate for this lack of information, patients turn to online resources. This yields mixed results. On the one hand, there patients find patient organisations and activists who can provide reliable information and assistance. On the other hand, online search without guidance leads to unnecessary distress (“*And then it will depend on luck, if a mom trusts the Internet completely there will be a disaster*” R_SpB_3) or even puts patients at risk of becoming fraud victims.

Driven by solidarity, patients who have succeeded in acquiring reliable information try to make this process easier for new patients by sharing their knowledge and experience. For example, active patients sometimes become hubs where all types of helpful knowledge are collected and shared in various forms. Those can be advice about the best medical professionals, collections of “*trusted*” medical resources, instructions on protecting patients’ rights, and premade forms for official letters and complaints.

Patient communities address gaps in patients’ knowledge more systematically by establishing contacts with “*trusted*” doctors and lawyers and inviting them to patient conferences and Q&A sessions. In addition, they encourage horizontal exchange between patients via WhatsApp chats, where they can share practical advice and hands-on experiences about everything from using medical products to communicating with healthcare officials. Recognising the importance of being a “*knowledgeable, literate*” patient, communities and activists dedicate significant resources to knowledge accumulation and distribution:

[...] it seems to me that the great merit of patient organisations is that they educate patients and they have already made a big change. Patients [now] know that the drugs can be obtained. And it's even possible without lawyers, you can do it yourself, and there are patient organisations that can advise how to take these steps, it is not that scary, it's possible. So education, it is very, very important, these are matters of education. Legal aspects, medical aspects, this is how we do it, we are trying to carry out this difficult work. R_SpB_4

Mastering knowledge work allows patients to skilfully operate between different types of knowledge to steer their trajectories in the desired way. While staying (almost) invisible, even to patients themselves, it enables all other types of work and thus becomes invaluable for the successful construction of access to medicines.

5.2. Combining different types of work and building trajectories of access

We distinguished four types of patients work in shaping trajectories of access to medicines. Enacting different types of work, however, is not a linear or sequential process. Depending on the situation and problem, patients employ them cyclically or even simultaneously, with different types of work enabling or enhancing one another. It makes every access trajectory unique; however, the types of work are nevertheless recognisable. To demonstrate the peculiar intertwining of different types of work we present the case of a seven-year-old boy with phenylketonuria (PKU) and his mother – Veronika⁴ – who has successfully constructed access to medicines for her son.

PKU is a rare genetic disease managed by maintaining a low-protein diet and intaking a specially designed amino acid supplement throughout life. In Russia, all children with confirmed PKU are entitled to free amino acid supplements based on their official status as “*disabled children*”.

The access trajectory of Veronika’s son was first shaped by persisting work and knowing work enacted by his mother. When he was two months old, she noticed worrying symptoms – abnormal movements of his irises. She visited several doctors with no success – she was told that the problem is temporary and the symptoms will subside as soon as the baby grows. However, Veronika remained alert and kept visiting the doctors because this was her second child, and she believed those symptoms were not normal. She continued persisting and engaged the knowledge that she had as a mother to support her case until the diagnosis was established.

Further, Veronika needed to engage in complying work to receive the amino acid supplement her son was entitled to. However, alongside complying work, we can also notice the subtle knowledge work Veronika was doing. She both employed the knowledge she already had and collected new pieces of information. The process of receiving the drug turned out to be complicated and non-transparent, and although the supplement was procured and delivered to a pharmacy, Veronika was not informed about it. Instead, she tried to establish when the medicine would be provided by calling different authorities who could give her any information. As she expressed, she was “*tossed*” between different phone numbers until she reached the regional governor’s office, where she was finally promised that her problem would be addressed immediately. The woman who made that promise provided Veronika with clear instructions on where to go and which hospital staff had the responsibility to help her. This woman supported Veronika throughout the entire process, and she received the supplement.

After these events, Veronika engaged in extensive knowledge work to provide her son with the best possible care. Through online sources, she found information about a doctor in St. Petersburg who specialises in children with PKU, and she became determined to bring her son to that doctor’s office. That doctor met Veronika’s expectations of high-quality help and also provided her with contact information for a PKU patient organisation. Through that organisation, she met other parents of children with PKU, which further proved essential in dealing with everyday practical problems (knowing work) and securing access to amino acid supplements.

Securing access to the supplement serves as an example of adjustment work done by patients’ families, as failures in the healthcare system were addressed informally with heavy reliance on trust and solidarity. After November 2020, because of bureaucratic budgeting and

⁴ The name was changed.

procurement changes, patients with PKU began to receive a year's supply of the amino supplement instead of a stock for one month. Because the daily supplement dose depends on a patient's weight, and children's weight changes significantly in one year, parents started to face shortages by the end of the year. Furthermore, the new procurement system worked with delays, and the supplement was unavailable for several months. To address these problems, Veronika borrowed several packages of the supplement from another patient's mother, promising to return the same amount as soon as the state provided it.

Activities organised by parents of children with PKU serve as another example of adjustment work that focuses more on compensating for absent services than on access to medications. Because children with PKU must follow a very strict diet and because no dietary menu is officially developed and approved by healthcare and education authorities, no organisation providing summer recreation wants to accept these children. In response, parents have organised their summer retreats where children with PKU could socialise without being bullied or risking their health, both of which they experience daily in regular educational settings. According to Veronika, the patient organisation is trying to change the situation through educational authorities by writing official requests to develop a dietary menu for children with PKU. So far, however, it appears that more complying work must be done for these children to access a safer educational environment.

6. Discussion

In health policy studies, access to medicines has been approached as a characteristic of a healthcare system determined by economic and institutional factors. Our analysis, however, demonstrated that access is not an automatic result of institutions' functioning, but rather a process patients must constantly and actively construct. Following the notion of co-production and STS tradition we demonstrated that patients are not just users of the complex access systems but their co-creators.

We approached access to medicines as a trajectory shaped by various actors. In the existing literature on illness trajectories (Corbin and Strauss, 1985, 1988), all activities related to medicines were categorised as illness-related work, and accessing medicines was not extensively discussed. This paper demonstrated the variety of such activities and distinguished four types of patients' work aimed at securing access to medicines: persisting work, complying work, adjusting work, and knowing work. We identified these types of work based on what appears paramount to building a successful trajectory of access to medicines. We learned that being a knowledgeable patient as well as a persistent, even annoying one, bears positive results. We learned that procedures of medicines' provision created by the state are complicated and non-straightforward and complying with them requires skill and effort. We learned that even when the system fails, there is still hope in community solidarity. We learned that trajectories of access are, as Singh (2016) argued, shaped by people's hopes and dreams of the future serving at times as the only driver motivating patients to keep fighting for access to medicines.

Besides identifying the four types of work, we demonstrated that none of them exists independently or is done in a pre-determined order. As with the types of work involved in managing chronic illnesses at home (Corbin and Strauss, 1988), we see that works done to build access to medicines are also intertwined, co-dependant, and combined in response to the circumstances. Thus, for example, we observe how, while complying (e.g., waiting for the drug to be available), patients adjust (e.g., borrowing the drug) by employing their knowledge (e.g., of where and whom to ask).

Moreover, our analysis vividly demonstrated the iterative nature of access trajectories. On the one hand, many of the described patients' practices emerge in response to the dysfunctions of the Russian system of drug provision. For example, heavy bureaucratisation and lack of financial resources lead to shortened interactions with doctors, ever-present delays and unacceptably long waiting lines to which patients

must adapt, usually via adjusting and complying work. Unequally distributed healthcare provision leads to dispersion of diagnostic facilities across the country complicating diagnostic journey and making patients respond with persisting. Lack of holistic support leaves patients hand to hand with their disease which motivates them to engage in knowing work. These patients' practices routinely allow to "get things done" within existing system of drug provision.

On the other hand, adjusting, adapting, bridging that patients do to create access to medicines has its transformative power. Since most of the practices described above are informal, like other informal practices they are ambivalent (Ledeneva et al., 2018). They both sustain and transform the existing healthcare system. As described above, patients' work allow for healthcare system to exist without major collapses but at the same time it leaves patients weary and frustrated by the system's functioning. This uneasiness and dissatisfaction sometimes transforms into system changes that in turn affect patients' access trajectories. For example, parents of children with PKU managed to counter the revocation of the disability status of their children; patients with Coeliac disease succeeded in demanding the development of an official dietary menu that can be used in educational and recreational facilities. Although small in scale, these changes affected both patients' access to medicines and their approach to the system and empowered them to protect their rights.

We recognise that our work has limitations. As mentioned above, all our research participants were recruited through and thus had connections with patient organisations. We learned that these communities provide patients with significant resources to make their trajectories of access to medicines successful. Not all patients have access to these communities and, thus, resources. Moreover, restricted resources do not allow many patients to establish the correct diagnosis in the first place. Both groups of patients are not represented in our study. Thus, our paper only focuses on those types of work that are done by patients who have sufficient resources – time, education, network, money, etc. – to do them. In this sense, our research is similar to that of Singh, who concluded that "the parenting work and trajectories of care identified in this study required a certain level of social and cultural capital" (Singh, 2016, p. 1118). We assume that access trajectories of patients who lack these capitals take very different shapes from what we described, thus further research that would shed led on these patients' work and struggles is needed.

Besides contributing to the body of literature that discusses trajectories, our paper provides some other theoretical takeaways. One is related to the invisibility of patients' accessing work. In sociology of health and medicine work that patients must undertake to achieve their healthcare goals is often conceptualised as invisible work. Along these lines, Strauss et al. (1982) analysed the activities of patients in hospitals (e.g., giving blood for a test), Oudshoorn (2008) described efforts put by patients into engaging with technologies, Ancker et al. (2015) studied work done by patients to manage their personal healthcare data, and Arteaga (2022), Wolters et al. (2020) and Prainsack (2017) drew attention to the work of patients needed to participate in clinical trials. This body of literature stands in line with other research on invisible work, such as housework done by women (Daniels, 1987) or organising work done by nurses (Allen, 2014). Invisible work is usually conceptualised as value-creating activities that are overlooked, undervalued, usually done outside of traditional workplaces, and often by those from whom that work is socially expected. In our research, we have demonstrated that patients' practices of creating access to medicines are essential for patients' survival and wellbeing. They take effort and resources, creating value that is the best care possible. These practices are also rarely regarded as work. Instead, they are taken as something naturally expected of a family or an ill person. Thus, we can consider patients' access practices yet another type of invisible work done by patients. We highlighted this finding via names of the four types of work identified above – "persisting work" and not just "persisting practices", "knowing work" and not just "knowing practices", etc.

Another theoretical contribution we want to highlight relates to the knowledge work done by patients. The STS field has extensively discussed patients' expertise and lay knowledge. For example, Rabeharisoa et al. (2014) showed how patients engaged scientists in research by providing them with access to evidence about the disease collected by patients. Patients' knowledge traditionally discussed in STS typically includes a biomedical understanding of the disease and embodied experiences. In our research, however, we demonstrated that patients' knowledge goes beyond that and includes knowledge of bureaucratic and legislative systems and ways of navigating, complying with, and adjusting to them. In many instances, research participants named these particular components of lay knowledge as essential for an "expert patient".

In this paper, we discussed the work done by patients to construct access to medicines in Russia. Our empirical findings are situated in this specific context. However, generated insights can guide research on access to medicines in other contexts. In Russia, the work done by patients is necessitated by the complexity and inconsistency of bureaucratic procedures; however, this does not mean that in other, less complex and more consistent healthcare systems there is no work required on the side of patients to access medicines. Literature on health inequalities provides examples of how some patients (e.g. refugees (Bellamy et al., 2015), HIV-positive populations (Wood et al., 2003), etc.) struggle to get access to medicines in countries with comprehensive and affluent healthcare systems. These examples hint on invisible work patients have to perform anywhere to secure access, although further research is needed to understand how patients' work is shaped in different healthcare contexts.

Thus, we highlight the essential aspect of access to medicines usually overlooked in health policy literature – patients do not remain passive and static. Instead, they actively shape their trajectories of access by employing different types of work. They do this creative and skilful but invisible and undervalued work daily to ensure their own and their children's health. Therefore, we argue that access to medicines is not something stable, but something (re)created daily by the people both inside and outside our specific research context.

Credit information

Olga Temina: Conceptualization (equal), Investigation (lead), Writing – original draft (lead), Writing – review and editing (equal). Olga Zvonareva: Conceptualization (equal), Investigation (supporting), Supervision (equal), Writing – review and editing (equal). Klasien Horstman: Conceptualization (equal), Supervision (equal), Writing – review and editing (equal).

Declarations of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The anonymized data can be shared upon motivated request. Due to ethical and privacy concerns as well as high vulnerability of the research participants the data cannot be made publicly available.

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